

Metal Ion Interaction with Penicillins. Part-V. Formation and Stability of Mixed-ligand Complexes of Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper- and Zinc(II) with 6-Aminopenicillanic Acid and Nucleic Bases

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Equilibrium study on the mixed-ligand complex formation of M^{2+} ions ($M = Co, Ni, Cu$ and Zn) with 6-aminopenicillanic acid ($apaH^{\pm}$) and nucleic bases adenine, guanine, thymine, uracil (BH) and cytosine (B) in aqueous solution, ionic strength, $I = 0.1 M$ ($NaNO_3$) and at 37° has provided evidence of formation of a variety of complexes of the types, $M(apa)$, $M(B)$, $M(apa)(B)$, $M(apa)(B)(OH)$ and $M(apa)(B)(OH)_2$. Stability of these complexes has been characterised by $\log \beta_{M(apa)(B)}^M$ and $\Delta \log K_M$ values. Stability of $M(apa)$, $M(B)$ and $M(apa)(B)$ complexes has been found to follow the order : $Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Co^{II} > Zn^{II}$ with regard to the metal ions, and the order : guanine > adenine > uracil \approx thymine > cytosine with regard to the nucleic bases. Acidity of the coordinated water molecules in $M(apa)(B)$ complexes has been found to increase with the stability constant of such complexes. Cytosine is found to form complexes of least stability with all the four metal ions.

Mixed-ligand complexes commonly occur in biological fluids as millions of potential ligands are likely to compete for metal ions found in vivo, i.e., Na, K, Mg, Ca, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn and Mo^I . It is well known that ternary complexes play important roles in biological processes, as exemplified by many instances in which enzymes are known to be activated by metal ions². Ternary complexes have also been implicated in the storage and transport of active substances through biological membranes. These phenomena are strongly dependent upon the formation of higher order complexes and the nature of involved metal ions³. Substituted purine and pyrimidine constitute the structure of DNA and RNA molecules. The metal complexes of purine and pyrimidine nucleotides are involved in many biochemical systems, particularly in genetic information transfer, energy transfer and oxidative phosphorylation. Therefore, a systematic study of the interaction of biological metal ions with antibiotic drugs, in the presence of purine and

pyrimidine bases, may yield useful informations for elucidating the molecular mechanism of drug actions. With this in mind, we studied the mixed-ligand complex formation of bivalent Co, Ni, Cu and Zn with 6-aminopenicillanic acid (hereafter $apaH^{\pm}$, 1) and the nucleic bases, viz. adenine, guanine, thymine, uracil (hereafter, BH) and cytosine (hereafter, B) in aqueous solution at 37° maintaining a constant ionic strength $I = 0.1 M$. Results of such study have been described here.

Results and Discussion

The protonated ligand species, $apaH_2^{\pm}$ titrates as a biprotic acid. The ligand species apa^{\pm} ,

coordinates Cu^{II} as a (N, O) bidentate ligand using the amino nitrogen and carbonyl oxygen and as a (N, S) bidentate ligand using the amino nitrogen and thiazolidine sulphur atoms to form 1 : 1 metal : ligand complexes only⁴.

The ternary $\text{M}(\text{apa})(\text{B})$ complexes are characterised by $\log \beta_{\text{M}(\text{apa})(\text{B})}^{\text{M}}$ and $\Delta \log K_{\text{M}}$ values⁵, whereas those of the quaternary hydroxo complexes may be characterised by the deprotonation constants of the corresponding aqua complexes. A positive value of $\Delta \log K_{\text{M}}$ or a value that is less negative than -0.60 , suggests favoured formation of ternary $\text{M}(\text{apa})(\text{B})$ complexes⁵ over the binary ones. Deprotonation constants, $K_{\text{M}(\text{apa})(\text{B})}^{\text{H}}$ and $K_{\text{M}(\text{apa})(\text{B})}^{2\text{H}}$ of the aqua complexes, $\text{M}(\text{apa})(\text{B})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$, may be calculated using the relations,

$$\log \beta_{\text{M}(\text{apa})(\text{B})(\text{OH})}^{\text{M}} = \log \beta_{\text{M}(\text{apa})(\text{B})}^{\text{M}} + \log K_{\text{M}(\text{apa})(\text{B})}^{\text{H}} \quad (1)$$

$$\log \beta_{\text{M}(\text{apa})(\text{B})(\text{OH})_2}^{\text{M}} = \log \beta_{\text{M}(\text{apa})(\text{B})(\text{OH})}^{\text{M}} + \log K_{\text{M}(\text{apa})(\text{B})(\text{OH})}^{\text{H}} \quad (2)$$

$$\log K_{\text{M}(\text{apa})(\text{B})}^{2\text{H}} = \log K_{\text{M}(\text{apa})(\text{B})}^{\text{H}} + \log K_{\text{M}(\text{apa})(\text{B})(\text{OH})}^{\text{H}} \quad (3)$$

$\beta_{\text{M}(\text{apa})(\text{B})}^{\text{M}}$ values of the ternary $\text{M}(\text{apa})(\text{B})$ complexes (Table 1) are found to be in the Irving-

Fig. 1. Species distribution curves of $\text{Ni}^{2+}/\text{apaH}/\text{adenine}$ system at $37 \pm 0.1^\circ$: (1) apaH_2^+ , (2) apaH , (3) apa^- , (4) adH_2^+ , (5) adH , (6) ad^- , (7) Ni^{2+} , (8) $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})^+$, (9) $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$, (10) $\text{Ni}(\text{apa})^+$, (11) $\text{Ni}(\text{ad})^+$, (12) $\text{Ni}(\text{apa})(\text{ad})$, (13) $\text{Ni}(\text{apa})(\text{ad})(\text{OH})^-$ and (14) $\text{Ni}(\text{apa})(\text{ad})(\text{OH})_2^{2-}$

Williams order : $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} < \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$. Analysis of the species distribution curves (Figs. 1-3) reveals the existence of the following com-

Fig. 2. Species distribution curves of $\text{Cu}^{2+}/\text{apaH}/\text{guanine}$ system at $37 \pm 0.1^\circ$: (1) apaH_2^+ , (2) apaH , (3) apa^- , (4) guaH_2^+ , (5) guaH , (6) gua^- , (7) Cu^{2+} , (8) $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$, (9) $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$, (10) $\text{Cu}(\text{apa})^+$, (11) $\text{Cu}(\text{gua})^+$, (12) $\text{Cu}(\text{apa})(\text{gua})$, (13) $\text{Cu}(\text{apa})(\text{gua})(\text{OH})^-$ and (14) $\text{Cu}(\text{apa})(\text{gua})(\text{OH})_2^{2-}$.

Fig. 3. Species distribution curves of $\text{Cu}^{2+}/\text{apaH}/\text{cytosine}$ system at $36 \pm 0.1^\circ$: (1) apaH_2^+ , (2) apaH , (3) apa^- , (4) cytH^+ , (5) cyt , (6) Cu^{2+} , (7) $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$, (8) $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$, (9) $\text{Cu}(\text{apa})^+$, (10) $\text{Cu}(\text{cyt})^{2+}$, (11) $\text{Cu}(\text{apa})(\text{cyt})^+$ and (12) $\text{Cu}(\text{apa})(\text{cyt})(\text{OH})$.

plexation equilibria for the formation of mixed-ligand $\text{M}(\text{apa})(\text{B})$ complexes with adenine, guanine and cytosine, at $\text{pH} < 5$,

Charges of the complex species are omitted for simplicity. At higher $\text{pH} (> 7)$, these ternary complexes (2) undergo successive deprotonation of coordinated water molecules, to produce the quaternary hydroxo complexes (3, 4) according to,

Fig. 4. Species distribution curves of $\text{Cu}^{2+}/\text{apaH}/\text{thymine}$ system at $37 \pm 0.1^\circ$: (1) apaH_2^+ , (2) apaH , (3) apa^- , (4) thyH , (5) thy^- , (6) Cu^{2+} , (7) $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$, (8) $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$, (9) $\text{Cu}(\text{apa})^+$, (10) $\text{Cu}(\text{thy})^+$, (11) $\text{Cu}(\text{apa})(\text{thy})$, (12) $\text{Cu}(\text{apa})(\text{thy})(\text{OH})^-$ and (13) $\text{Cu}(\text{apa})(\text{thy})(\text{HO})_2^{2-}$.

Analogous nature of the species distribution curves (Fig. 4) of $\text{M}(\text{apa})(\text{uracil}$ or $\text{thymine})$ systems indicate the formation of similar type of complexes and the stability of these complexes are also comparable. Species distribution curves of $\text{Cu}^{2+}/\text{apa}^-/\text{B}$ systems with uracil and thymine, however, indicate the formation of $\text{Cu}(\text{apa})(\text{B})(\text{OH})$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{apa})(\text{B})(\text{OH})_2$ complexes according to,

The pK^{H} values of the coordinated water molecules are found to be much lower than the pK_w of

TABLE I—STABILITY CONSTANTS* OF BINARY, TERNARY AND QUATERNARY HYDROXO COMPLEXES IN THE $\text{M}/\text{apaH}/\text{B}$ SYSTEMS ($\text{M}=\text{Co}^{\text{II}}$, Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} AND Zn^{II} ; $\text{BH} = \text{ADENINE, GUANINE, URACIL, THYMINE}$; $\text{B} = \text{CYTOSINE}$) IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION AT $37 \pm 0.1^\circ$ AT A CONSTANT IONIC STRENGTH, $I = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (NaNO_3)

Constant	B M	Adenine	Guanine	Uracil	Thymine	Cytosine
$\text{pK}_{\text{BH}_2}^{\text{H}}$	—	3.96	3.08	—	—	—
$\text{pK}_{\text{BH}}^{\text{H}}$	—	9.38	8.92	9.33	9.70	4.40
$\log K_{\text{M}(\text{B})}^{\text{M}}$	Co	8.26	8.48	3.82	3.79	1.60
	Ni	8.41	8.64	3.95	3.91	1.70
	Cu	8.65	9.89	4.36	4.31	1.85
	Zn	8.28	8.54	3.78	3.79	1.55
$\log \beta_{\text{M}(\text{apa})(\text{B})}^{\text{M}}$	Co	11.72	11.98	7.27	7.22	5.04
	Ni	12.09	12.38	7.62	7.57	5.38
	Cu	13.17	13.48	8.85	8.78	6.57
	Zn	10.55	10.82	5.03	4.94	2.83
$\Delta \log K_{\text{M}}$	Co	0.33	0.37	0.32	0.30	0.31
	Ni	0.38	0.44	0.37	0.36	0.38
	Cu	0.42	0.49	0.39	0.37	0.62
	Zn	0.37	0.38	—	—	—
$\text{pK}_{\text{M}(\text{apa})(\text{B})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2}^{\text{H}}$	Co	7.55	7.45	7.45	7.49	7.53
	Ni	7.20	7.04	7.27	7.32	7.31
	Cu	7.05	6.94	6.48	6.52	6.52
	Zn	8.05	8.01	—	—	—
$\text{pK}_{\text{M}(\text{apa})(\text{B})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})}^{\text{H}}$	Co	8.96	8.82	10.32	—	—
	Ni	8.52	8.42	9.77	9.81	—
	Cu	8.25	8.12	8.78	8.84	—
	Zn	9.32	9.26	—	—	—

* Limits of error in the constants : ± 0.05 in log units. pK_w of water at 37° : 13.62 (Ref. 16). $\log K_{\text{M}(\text{apa})}^{\text{M}}$: Co (3.13), Ni (3.30), Cu (4.10), Zn (1.90); $\text{pK}_{\text{M}}^{\text{H}}$ and $\text{pK}_{\text{M}}^{2\text{H}}$: Co (8.21 and 17.29), Ni (8.05 and 16.83), Cu (6.29 and 13.05), Zn (7.84 and 14.87) at 37° , $I = 0.1 \text{ M}$ NaNO_3 (Ref. 14).

water under identical condition⁶. This is due to the delocalisation of metal $d\pi$ electrons, over to the vacant $d\pi$ orbitals of sulphur atom through a structural change within the $M(apa)(B)(H_2O)_2$ complexes in which the coordinated apa^- ligand changes from (N, O) bidentate to a (N, S) bidentate ligand with rise of pH, according to eqm. (12).

Ternary $Zn(apa)(B)$ complexes are not formed in significant amount in any of the $Zn^{2+}/apa^-/$ nucleic base systems, possibly due to the lower affinity of Zn^{II} for S-donor atom, as compared to Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} . All the ternary systems with Zn^{II} are dominated by the hydroxo species, $Zn(OH)^+$ and $Zn(OH)_2$ at $pH > 7$, though small amounts of binary $Zn(apa)^+$ and $Zn(B)$ complexes are also formed at lower pH values. Sharp rise of the concentration of $Zn(OH)_2$, in spite of flat decline of $Zn(OH)^+$ at $pH > 10$, indicates the existence of following equilibria,

in addition to hydrolytic equilibria of $Zn^{2+}(aq)$ ion.

Stability of the ternary complexes are found to be in the order : guanine > adenine > thymine \approx uracil > cytosine, with regard to the nucleic base ligands. Purine bases, viz. adenine (5) and guanine (6) coordinate metal ions at the N(7) and N(9) atoms⁷. In some adenine complexes, however, metallation also occurs at N(3) and N(1) positions⁷, as is evident from the fact that in acid medium protonation on adenine takes place at N(1) near pH 4.0 and deprotonation at N(9) hydrogen⁸ near pH 10. On the other hand, protonation and positive charge placement take place with guanine near pH 3 at N(7) and deprotonation occurs near pH at N(1)⁸.

Chelation may, however, favour one ligand site over the other. Direct chelation between the N(7) of purines and substituent in the 6-position, e.g. NH_2 group in adenine and carbonyl oxygen atom in guanine is not possible. Because basicity of NH_2 group in adenine is reduced considerably due to electron delocalisation into the ring system. As a result of this, the NH_2 group is nearly coplanar with the ring system and the amino nitrogen to carbon bond lengths are about 0.06 Å shorter in adenine than in aniline, indicating the appreciable double bond

character of the C–NH₂ bond⁹. In case of guanine, the strength of the metal-oxygen bond can not compensate for the distortion and strains introduced into the 5-membered chelate ring. Indirect chelation involving N(7) and substituents at C(6) is however indicated from crystal structure study of certain metal complexes of purines¹⁰. In adenine complexes, the 6-NH₂ group serves as a hydrogen bond donor to an acceptor ligand attached to the N(7) bound metal ion. In contrast, in guanine complexes the 6-oxo group functions as a hydrogen bond acceptor to a hydrogen bond donor ligand attached to the N(7) bound metal ion. Water has been shown to serve as the acceptor ligand in adenine complexes and the donor ligand in 6-oxopurine complexes¹¹. It seems likely that in aqueous solution, a water ligand would commonly function as the bridge between the 6-amino or 6-oxopurine substituents and the N(7) bound metal ion. Indirect chelation may be a contributing factor favouring N(7) over N(1) as a metal ion bonding site in purines. Requirements for a hydrogen bond donor ligand appear to be more stringent than those for a hydrogen bond acceptor ligand. This favours stronger chelation in the guanine complexes than that in adenine complexes. As a result of this, the guanine complexes are more stable than the corresponding complexes with adenine.

Cytosine (7), uracil (8) and thymine (9) act as monodentate ligands and coordinate metal ions

at the N(3) atoms. Cytosine is protonated at N(3) near pH 4. Both protonation and metallation of cytosine occur at N(3)¹². Any chelation introduced by an interaction with O(2) is so weak as to contribute quite negligibly to the stability of the complexes in aqueous solution¹³.

Protonation of uracil and thymine occurs in neutral solutions with $pK_a \sim 9.5$ for N(3) and ~ 14 for N(1). It is evident from this equilibrium study that metallation of this ligands is strongly dependent on pH of the solutions. This indicates C(2)-oxygen coordination in acidic solutions. N(3) coordination in slightly basic solutions and N(1) coordination with unsubstituted bases in strongly basic solutions. Therefore, metallation at N(1) and N(3) of uracil and thymine takes place with release of the N(1) and N(3) bound protons^{13,14}. In aqueous solutions metal ion coordination at N(3) can take place if the N(3) proton is displaceable by the metal ion prior to hydroxo complex formation and precipitation¹⁵. The higher stability of uracil and thymine complexes over the corresponding complexes with cytosine is due to their higher basicity at N(3). The possibility of indirect chelation in uracil and thymine complexes through hydrogen bonding as those in the guanine complexes via a water molecule can not, however, be ruled out.

Experimental

A.R. quality 6-aminopenicillanic acid (Aldrich) was directly used. Adenine, guanine, cytosine, thymine and uracil and also the other reagents used were of A.R. grade. All the solutions were prepared in double-distilled CO₂-free water. Carbonatefree NaOH solution¹⁶ was used as the titrant. The procedure for the pH-metric titration was the same as described in our earlier publications^{4,17}. For the determination of binary M²⁺-ligand stability constants, the M²⁺ : ligand ratios in the experimental solutions were kept as 1 : 5, 1 : 8 and 1 : 10. For studying the mixed-ligand complexation equilibria, the M²⁺ : apaH[±] : B ratio was 1 : 1 : 1.

Stability constants, β_{pqrs} , of $[M_p(\text{apa})_q(\text{B})_r(\text{OH})_s]$ complexes may be defined according to

$$\beta_{pqrs} = \frac{[M]_p[\text{apa}]_q[\text{B}]_r[\text{OH}]_s}{[M]^p[\text{apa}]^q[\text{B}]^r[\text{OH}]^s} \quad (16)$$

Charges have been dropped for clarity. p , q , r and s are all stoichiometric coefficients; p , q and r are positive numbers or zero, whereas s is a negative number for protonated species and a positive number for a hydroxo species.

The constants, β_{pqrs} , were calculated with the aid of SCOGS programme¹⁸, run on a PC-XT computer system. Proton-ligand and M^{2+} -ligand binary stability constants^{4,8,12,13,19} supplied to the computer as input data, were also determined under identical conditions.

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